

Comparative Relationship between Infrastructural Development and Biodiversity Loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to investigate the relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of this study, a null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study. A review of related literature was carried out based on the variable of this study. The survey research design was considered useful for the study. The research adopted multiple sampling approaches. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 234 subjects used as sample in each ward in the Local Government Area. A fifteen-item modified four (4) points Likert scale questionnaire titled Infrastructural Development and Biodiversity Loss Questionnaire (IDBLQ) was the instrument used for data collection. To test the hypothesis formulated for the study, Pearson's product moment correlation statistical tools was used for data analysis. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 alpha level. The results from data analysis and hypothesis testing indicated that there is a significant relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in the study area. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that relevant authorities should ensure that infrastructural development projects are properly located in line with laid down policies and regulations in order to prevent continuous loss of biodiversity.

Keyword: infrastructure, development, biodiversity loss, Akamkpa Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Introduction

Biodiversity, the variation of life on Earth, is a major factor in nature's resilience. In a bio diverse ecosystem, the environment changes and some organisms can no longer thrive, others can take their place and fulfill essential functions. It is often the most overlooked species that are the most important to healthy ecosystems. Insects, for example, play an essential role in pollinating flowering plants one of the foods we eat depends on pollinators.

Jacob (2017) asserts that healthy ecosystems provide us with many essentials we take for granted. Plants converts energy from the sun and also makes it available to other life forms bacteria and other living organisms break down organic matter into nutrients which help provide plants with healthy soil to grow in. Agents of pollination are essential in plants reproduction and therefore, help to guarantee food product for mankind. Plants and oceans act as major carbon sinks. Biodiversity provides us with clean air, fresh water, good quality soil and crop pollination. It helps us fight climate change and adapt to it as well as reduce the impact of natural hazards. Since living organisms interact in dynamic ecosystems, the

disappearance of one species can have a far-reaching impact on the food chain. It is impossible to know exactly what the consequences of mass extinctions would be for humans, but we do know that for now the diversity of nature allows us to thrive. Biodiversity is very vital to the survival of mankind and as such should be considered as an important component of human existence. It provides for the various basic needs of man and the sustainability of the ecosystems. This emphasizes the role of biodiversity in the sustainability of the human race (Fred, 2016).

The loss of biodiversity has become a source of Concern to various stakeholders in environment and ecological ecosystem. The Continuous disappearance of various plant and animal species has been a regular feature and does not seem feasible in recent years. This is because man is inventing new technology and equipment that will aid improved harvesting process, processing, storing and transportation of biological diversity for various purposes. These purposes stem from domestic, commercial, industrial and other process alike. The continuous depletion, endangerment and extinction of species have affected the balance of nature. Government and other agencies involved in biodiversity conservation have introduced various policies that would regulate the use of biodiversity. Some of these include the introduction of Environmental or conservation education, the enactment of legislation among other (Obi, 2017).

These efforts have yielded little or no result with regards to the reduction in the loss of biodiversity. People seem so determined to exploit biological resources as a major source of their livelihood. This accounts mostly for the insignificant result obtained from the intervention activities of both government and non-governmental organizations. Several factors have been identified as possible determinants of the loss of biodiversity. Albert (2015) states that the process of providing certain infrastructure could lead to the destruction of vegetation cover that houses several species of plant and animals. The provision of these infrastructure might require the cutting down of large forested areas or of certain habitats. These activities could pose severe threat to biodiversity leading to their endangerment or extinction. These the researcher to investigate how assumptions motivated infrastructural development relate with biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State.

The findings of this study will be relevant to students, residents of the host communities, the Ministry of Environment, non-governmental organizations, policy makers and researchers.

Students of environmental education and other disciplines will see the findings of this study as a source of acquiring relevant knowledge on the phenomenon under study. Inhabitants of the host communities will also be sensitized through the findings of this study on how their various activities relate with biodiversity loss, in order to promote sustainable forest management. The Ministry of Environment will also be further sensitized on how the activities engaged by rural dwellers impact of the loss of biological diversity in order to help provide alternative livelihood where necessary. Non-governmental organizations working on biodiversity conservation and management will see the findings of this study as a relevant document that would help them achieve their intervention goals and objectives. Policy makers will also see the findings of this study as a source of baseline data for formulated new policies that would promote effective biodiversity conservation and management. Researchers intending to conduct a similar study in other locations or on a broader Scope will see the findings of this study as a reference material for their studies.

Humans are constantly involved in a variety of activities that tend to impact negatively on the quality and well-being of the environment. This continuous degradation of the environment has resulted in the destruction of plant and animal species. Akamkpa is blessed with abundance of biological diversity. There is a reasonable quantity of virgin forest still intact due to the long existing belief that, forests in the area harbour spirits which may hurt anyone that trespasses it. Despite the cultural taboos that prevent people from the indiscriminate use of biological diversity, it is common to see people young and old go into the forest without fear or respect to the cultural norms, values and belief system obtainable in the area. It is quite disturbing to see the rate at which biodiversity is been damaged, destroyed and taken away without any deliberate attempt to replace them. The fear is that, if nothing is done about the situation, sooner than possible biodiversity resources may completely disappear through extinction. This study was therefore geared towards attempting to find answers to the following question how do infrastructural development relate with biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State?

The following theory was considered as the framework for this study in order to help explain the interrelations among variables in the study.

Lanza's biocentric theory (1997); This theory was propounded by Robert Lanza in 1997. The theory holds that nature is sacred and as Such should be revered or emphasizing man's interdependence with nature further holds that the living and non-living things were created before man and therefore have their own right of existence inspite of man. The emphasis of this theory is that; man should live tenderly with nature in mutual or symbiotic existence. Africa culture and most indigenous the world-over before the advent of colonization were actually given to the biocentric worldview value judgement about nature. In fact, not only we the Africans or native tribes are conscious of their interdependence with nature, they even went as far as ascribing life and supernatural power to nature. All these, made it imperative to conserve nature.

The implication of this theory to the present study is that the biocentric theory promotes and lays the foundation for biodiversity conservation and management at various levels. This theory is against wanton destruction and unsustainable exploitation of biodiversity and emphasize that man is not superior to nature but should live in mutual or symbiotic relationship with it. Thus, considering the right of these natural resources to exist within the environment and their relevant to him justifies the view point of the biocentric theory. This theory is the basis for sustainable utilization and management of natural resources as well as sustainable development. Based on these, the conservation of biodiversity takes its roots from the value judgment of this theory.

The main purpose of this study was to investigate infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State, Specifically the study:

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated to guide the study:
There is no significant relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Literature Review

Infrastructural development and biodiversity loss

Infrastructure plays a key role in biodiversity loss, because of the impact associated with it on the environment. The negative and cooperate for fair trade products environmental impact of infrastructure can occur construction, operation upgrade and decommissioning of infrastructures. While similar environmental impacts such as the use of natural resources, changes in land use disturbances in the human environmental may occur in the construction and operational stages of most types of infrastructures, some sectors may bring about distinct impact. Some examples of these impacts are:

- i. Water infrastructure: This may result in excessive use of water resources or water pollution (leakages insufficient treatment of sewage).
- ii. Road infrastructure: This can fragment habitats and or cut off migration routes of animals leading to biodiversity loss.
- iii. Mining can bring about the decline in groundwater levels, mining waste and noise caused by explosion.

Even though development can be used as an opportunity to investigate the archaeology of the site and removal, restoration and conservation of items found, the adverse impacts it has on biodiversity still remains. These includes, removal of trees and in particular disruption of forests, can reduce their sustainability and their ability to act as a "sink" for carbon dioxide emissions and hence reduce their impact on global warming (Cervero, 2009). It can remove natural barriers to wind and weather which can add to soil erosion and impacts on other ecology. The construction and disposal of infrastructure can impact on the condition of the soil structure. For example, the use of vehicles and heavy machinery may cause compaction of soils, land clearance may lead to soil erosion and infrastructure work may cause soil contamination with toxic materials, there by scaring away any organism including man from his original habitat.

The large-scale problems of unprecedented population growth and inappropriate development are degrading the land, water and atmosphere thereby extinguishing earth's organisms and the habitats they inhabit. If we ignore and downplay the problems associated with infrastructure development and biodiversity loss in favour of our imperative personal or group gain, or national priorities, we are courting global disaster. Although population growth may not be the sole cause of environmental degradation, it is almost always an exacerbating factor (Barclay& Gray, 2016). As population pressures on land and other natural resource build. The need for more infrastructure development to meet their needs, the more intensity of natural disasters especially flood and drought that is possible of forcing organisms to migrate from their natural habitat or relocate to another habitat thereby causing biodiversity loss to occur and the effects, more tragic (Ephraim, 2016).

Biodiversity is irreversible to species that are lost. The potential impact on the human condition, on the fabric of the earth's living systems, and on the process of evolution is immense. Biologically diversity is the variety of life forms, the genetic diversity they contain, and the assemblages they form, biological system, whether tundra, forests, savannahs, grasslands, deserts lakes, rivers, wetlands, coastal communities, or marine ecosystems, are functionally complex, and this complexity is associated in often obscure ways, with the diversity of their component species.

Biodiversity is the variety of and variability among living organisms and the ecological complexes in which they occur. Diversity is the number of different items and their relative frequency. For biological diversity, these items are organized at many levels, ranging from chemical structures that are the molecular basis of heredity to complete ecosystems (OTA, 2017). To curb the problem associated with biodiversity loss through infrastructure development, there is a need to, as a matter of urgent importance; establish an international network of parliamentarians to undertake initiatives to mainstream biodiversity

conservation in infrastructure development. This is important to build political leadership for biodiversity conservation and strategic environmental impact assessment should be made to provide for holistic infrastructure planning and thereby increase the spatial and ecological conditions for green infrastructure to contribute to biodiversity preservation (Pease, 2014).

From the review done in this chapter of the various eminent scholars, it has been established that related literature reviewed has enabled the researcher to focus on the situation on ground as regard infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State. The depressing because available studies revealed that there is a relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss. The reviewed literature revealed that infrastructure development influence biodiversity loss. The review established that they still exist the problem of bush burning, and deforestation practices on the environment during infrastructural developments which lead to biodiversity loss in particular on the resources of the environment. It is on the basis of this gap identified that this research is carried out to encourage, and advised in other to assimilate information to enlighten and create awareness.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is the survey design. Survey research design is a research approach that attempts to systematically collect a data about a group of individuals (sample) who have the same characteristics, through the use of written or oral data collection instruments; interviews, questionnaires, telephone interview, mails, and internet, concerning participants' responses on facts, opinions, attitudes among others to enable the researcher study the group (population) of which the researcher has no control over the independent and dependent variables and the phenomenon is studied in its raw form as it is happening (Isangedighi, 2012). This design was chosen because this research is designed to investigate infrastructural development and biodiversity loss. The purpose of this study can be achieved through the survey research design.

This research was conducted in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State. It lies between latitude 8^o31.46" North of the Equator and longitude 5^o25'59.7" East of the Greenwich Meridian. Akamkpa Local Government Area has a land mass of 5003 square kilometres. It is bounded to the north by Biase Local Government Area to the south by Calabar Municipality, to the east by Odukpani Local Government Area and to the west by Itu Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Akamkpa Local Government Area is situated in the tropical rainforest belt with considerable amount of rainfall, which spans between April and November each year. These characterizes the crops Cultivated by its residents. The people are known for the production of food crops like maize, cassava, vegetables, spices, fruits among others at subsistence and commercial levels. The people also cultivate cash crops like oil palms, rubber, banana and plantain. The study area has a very rich cultural heritage, which is characterized by attractive festivals and amazing dances. There are several public educational institutions in the study area, which provide formal education to residents of the study area. The population of this research work consists of all adult residents in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State. They comprised individuals from various occupations including, hunters, students, and civil servants. The Fishermen, farmers, estimated population for the study is eighty-seven thousand three hundred and forty-two (228,543) persons (NPC, 2022).

The simple random sampling technique was adopted in selecting the communities used for the study. The researcher visited Akamkpa Local Government Forestry charge office to obtain the list of Communities in the study area. The names of all the twenty-eight communities were written on pieces of paper and folded into ball-like shapes, which were poured into a bowl. The paper-balls were properly mixed and the researcher picked seven paper-balls from the bowl representing twenty five percent of communities. The communities whose names appeared on the picked pieces of paper were selected for the study. To select the respondents used for the study, systematic random sampling technique was adopted. The researcher took time to number the houses in the study area. In each of the selected communities, the researcher selected every tenth house and in each of the selected houses, one respondent was selected. These individuals constituted the sample for the study. The sample for this study consisted of two hundred and thirty-four (234) respondents that were randomly selected from seven forest communities in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State. They were drawn from various occupations.

The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire. The instrument was developed by the researcher and titled "Infrastructural Development and Biodiversity Loss Questionnaire (IDBLQ) and divided into two sections, Section A contained items on respondents' personal data while section B was designed using four point modified Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). It contained fifteen items measuring the variables of the stud. Items 1-5 measured infrastructural development while items 6-15 measured biodiversity loss. The instrument used for data collection was presented to a lecturer in Environmental Education and two other lecturers in Test and Measurement for content and face validity. The instrument was scrutinized and necessary inputs made to improve the quality and ability of the

research instrument to measure what it is intended to measure. The suggestions made were put in place before a final copy was developed. The questionnaire was used to obtain relevant data from respondents. The researcher visited all the communities selected for the study to engage the respondents for data collection. In each community visited, the researcher obtained permission from the village head after explaining the purpose of her visit. Two hundred and thirty-four copies of the research instrument were administered and retrieved in five days. The responses obtained from respondents were scored accordingly to enable the researcher complete the coding procedure. For items that are positively worded, Strongly Agree (SA) was scored 4, Agree (A) 3, Disagree (D) 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) 1. The reverse scoring schedule was applied to negatively worded items in the questionnaire.

Presentation of Result

This chapter presents the results of data analysis and testing of hypothesis as well as their interpretation. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Table 1: Pearson product moment correlation analysis of the relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Variables	X	S.D	r-cal	Sig.
Infrastructural development	15.296	2.963	0.324*	0.001
Biodiversity loss	30.369	4.816		

Significant at 0.05, df = 232, critical r = 0.138

The independent variable in this hypothesis is infrastructural development while the dependent variable is biodiversity loss. Pearson product moment correlation statistical tool was used for data analysis. The result obtained from analysis is data and testing of hypothesis in the study is presented in table 1. The result of analysis presented in table 1 shows that the calculated r-value of 0.324 is higher than the p-value of 0.001 at 0.05 level of significance with 232 degree of freedom. This implies that the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Discussion of findings

Infrastructural development and biodiversity loss

The finding obtained from analysis of data and testing of hypothesis in the study revealed that the null hypothesis was rejected. The implication of this finding is that there was a significant relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State. The reason for this finding could be that as population continue to grow across various communities in the study area, there has been an increasing development of infrastructure. The need to build new schools, markets, health Centres, roads, churches among others has increased the pressure on biodiversity through the destruction of their natural habitats. In the course of this doing this, many species of flora and fauna have been displaced, endangered and even extinct. No infrastructure is developed in a vacuum but on a particular sphere of the environment. This has its attendant consequences on the biodiversity that once inhabited such area because they are usually displaced, destroyed or modified in the process.

This finding is in agreement with that of Ephraim (2016) who reported that the large-scale problems of unprecedented population growth and inappropriate development are degrading the land, water and atmosphere thereby extinguishing earth's organisms and the habitats they inhabit. If we ignore and downplay the problems associated with infrastructure development and biodiversity loss in favour of our imperative personal or group gain, or national priorities, we are courting global disaster. Although population growth may not be the sole cause of environmental degradation, it is almost always an exacerbating factor. As population pressures on land and other natural resource build. The need for more infrastructure development to meet their needs, the more intensity of natural disasters especially flood and drought that is possible of forcing organisms to migrate from their natural habitat or relocate to another habitat thereby causing biodiversity loss to occur and the effects, more tragic.

The finding of this study also supported that of OTA (2017) who revealed that Biodiversity is the variety of and variability among living organisms and the ecological complexes in which they occur. Diversity is the number of different items and their relative frequency. For biological diversity, these items are organized at many levels, ranging from chemical structures that are the molecular basis of heredity to complete ecosystems (OTA, 2017). To curb the problem associated with biodiversity loss through infrastructure development, there is a need to, as a matter of urgent importance; establish an international network of parliamentarians to undertake initiatives to mainstream biodiversity conservation in infrastructure development. This is important to build political leadership for biodiversity conservation and strategic environmental impact assessment should be made to provide for holistic infrastructure planning and thereby increase the spatial and ecological conditions for green infrastructure to contribute to biodiversity preservation.

Conclusion

The main purpose of this study was to investigate and present findings on anthropogenic activities and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State. The findings obtained from analysis of data and testing of hypothesis in the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in the study area. With the above result it was concluded that there is a significant relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Recommendation

The researcher made the following recommendations based on the findings obtained in the study;

1. Residents in the study area should be regularly and adequately sensitized on the danger of uncontrolled bush burning during development in order to prevent loss of biodiversity
2. Relevant authorities should ensure that infrastructural development projects are properly located in line with laid down policies and regulations in order to prevent continuous loss of biodiversity.

References

- Albert, S. L. (2015). Opportunities and challenges for the inclusion of soil improving crops in vegetable production systems. *Horticultural Science*, 27:754-758.
- Barclay, C. & Gray, M. (2016). *Land use and planning law*. London: University Press
- Cervero, R. (2009). Transport infrastructure and the environment in the global south sustainable mobility and urbanism. *Journal of Urban Regional Development*, 4:171-179
- Ephraim, G. C. (2016). Conservation impact of commercial wildlife farming of porcupines in Kenya. *Biological Conservation*, 12(3):176-184
- Fred, C. K. (2016). Perception of people and its implication in the attainment of sustainable development in developing countries. *International Journal of Ecology*, 3 (7):36-45
- Isangedighi, A. J. (2012). *Research methods and statistics in education and social sciences*. Calabar: Mandela Printing Press
- Jacob, B. (2017). Complementary of light and water use in tropical agro-forests: Theoretical model outline, performance and sensitivity, *Forest Ecology Management*. 102, 259-274.
- Lanza, R. (1997). *Promoting environmentalism for sustainable development*. London: McGraw Press Ltd.
- Obi, D. E. (2017). Livelihood activities and biodiversity loss in Boki Local Government Area of Cross River State. *International Journal of Social Science Research*, 3(3):264-272
- Obi, F. O. (2017). *Improving agricultural extension services for environmental conservation and management in developing countries*, Lagos: Cambiasso printing press Ltd.
- OTA (2017). *Dimensions of interaction between man and the environment: Implication for sustainable development*. Ibadan: Fumilayo press Ltd.
- Pease, B. D. (2014). Infrastructure investment opportunities for public safety plans.